

Can Cochlear Ion Transport Affect Cochlear Mechanics?

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Abstract. The potassium current circulating through the inner ear is instrumental in the mechanotransduction of auditory stimuli, allowing potassium ions (K^+) to enter and depolarize hair cells, leading to neurotransmission and electromotility. To maintain homeostasis, K^+ ions must return to the endolymph via cochlear marginal cells, which also help generate the endocochlear potential (EP). Our lab's computational models explore ion transport in the cochlea and its impact on hearing loss. Mutations in the I_{sK} current in marginal cells that increase channel conductance are linked to noise-induced hearing loss. We identified stable hypersensitive regions in transepithelial current profiles corresponding to elevated I_{sK} conductance. These regions correspond with regions where marginal cell swelling is predicted. Reducing NKCC transporter activity (to simulate furosemide block) on the marginal cell's basal side also creates hypersensitive regions. Experimentally, it has been shown that after the washout of furosemide, there is a lack of recovery of cochlear amplification compared to the EP. This has been attributed to unknown processes that affect the cochlear amplifier's operating point (OP). We hypothesize that physical changes in marginal cells may operate by a similar indirect mechanism on cochlear mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

Potassium (K^+) recirculation in the cochlea is accomplished by cochlear marginal cells, which also indirectly contribute to generating the endocochlear potential (EP) that provides the driving force for hair cell transduction. Our lab develops computational models of ion transport in the cochlea to understand the mechanisms of hearing loss and explore the relationship between ion transport and cochlear mechanics. Previous research has shown a link between mutations in the I_{sK} channel expressed on the apical side of marginal cells and the heightened susceptibility to noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) [1]. The precise mechanisms underlying this association remain unclear. The apical side of the marginal sides faces the endolymph, and the basal side faces the intrastrial fluid. We previously observed the emergence of a hypersensitive region within transepithelial current profiles across the marginal cell layer when the I_{sK} conductance and the potassium concentration in the intrastrial fluid were elevated [2]. The hypersensitive regions correspond to increased rates of ion transport across the marginal cell layer, with small changes in conditions having large effects on the transport rate. As noise exposure has been shown to increase potassium concentration in the intrastrial fluid [3], disruptions in marginal cell ion transport may cause NIHL.

Here, we first examine the stability of the steady-state solutions of the differential equations describing the system (in the hypersensitive regions of the transepithelial currents) using stability analysis to test the hypothesis that the mutation in I_{sK} causes instability in ion transport. Such effects have been previously observed in Hodgkin-Huxley models of ion channels [4]. In our case, the system was found to be stable, and we proceeded to examine other causes

for hypersensitivity. We noted that the hypersensitive regions corresponded to regions where the volume of the marginal cell was increasing. To validate these effects, we interpreted our results in light of earlier observations by Pike and Bosher [5] that blockage of the NKCC cotransporter by furosemide causes marginal cell swelling. This is particularly interesting as it has been recently shown that after recovery from furosemide administration, the endocochlear potential (EP) recovers on a faster time scale than cochlear amplification at best frequency [6]. The reasons for this observation are unclear but point to a growing appreciation for the role of ion homeostasis in cochlear mechanics through indirect effects on the mechanical properties of accessory cochlear structures. Our simulations lead us to hypothesize that changes in the physical properties of the marginal cells may also be a route to indirectly affect the cochlear amplifier's operating point.

METHODOLOGY AND COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

The model was adapted from the steady-state model developed by Quraishi and Raphael [7]. The model studied ion transport across a marginal cell situated between infinite baths with constant ionic composition on both apical and basolateral sides. In this model, the apical side is the fluid bath representing endolymph, and the basolateral side is the intrastrial space. Even though the ion concentrations of endolymph have been measured experimentally, ion concentrations in multiple other compartments in the cochlea like the intrastrial fluid are difficult to explore experimentally due to their small volumes. This model uses non-linear differential equations describing ion transport by ion channels, pumps, or leaks to show how ion transport across these small compartments affects their different ion concentrations. This model was previously used to study K^+ , Na^+ and Cl^- transport across marginal cells and how the transport rate of the Na/K ATPase the K^+ concentration in the intrastrial space affect the generation of the endocochlear potential [7,8].

To explore the relationship between mutation in the I_{sK} channel (the subunit KCNE1) and susceptibility to Noise-Induced Hearing Loss (NIHL), the conductivity of the I_{sK} channel on the apical side was increased. The transepithelial current contour plot w.r.t. the apical and basal concentrations was observed to develop a hypersensitive region at higher basal and apical K^+ concentrations when the K^+ permeability was increased. A stability analysis method was employed to determine the stability of these steady-state solutions. This was accomplished by computing the Jacobian matrix of the steady-state solutions. The signs of the eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrices indicated the stability of the solution. If $\lambda > 0$, the solution is unstable, and if $\lambda < 0$, the solution is stable.

The transepithelial K^+ current is given by $i_K^{te} = F \times J_K^{te}$, where $J_K^{te} = J_K^a + J_K^p$, is the transepithelial K^+ ion flux. Here J_K^a is the apical K^+ ion flux and J_K^p is the paracellular K^+ ion flux [7].

Let the steady state be described by $f(x)$, where x is a 6×1 vector describing the apical and basal membrane voltage, Na^+ , K^+ , and Cl^- ion concentrations, and the cell volume at the steady state. The stability of such steady-state solutions for similar non-linear systems has been previously studied using a linear stability analysis [4]. The Jacobian of this steady state is computed by;

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_n} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix}$$

We employ MATLAB R2023a to compute these values from the steady-state solutions of our system described by the non-linear differential equations. Then, we calculate the eigenvalues of these Jacobians and study the sign patterns of these eigenvalue matrices to analyze the stability of the solution.

We also calculated the cell volume for the corresponding apical and basal concentrations, assuming the marginal cell is in complete osmolar balance [7].

The cell volume change is computed as; $\frac{dw}{dt} = P_w A_a \left(\sum_k c_k^I + \frac{N_f}{w} - \sum_k c_k^A \right) + P_w A_b \left(\sum_k c_k^I + \frac{N_f}{w} - \sum_k c_k^B \right)$, where P_w is the permeability of the membrane to water, A_a and A_b are the apical and basolateral cell membrane area respectively, c_k^I , c_k^A and c_k^B are concentrations of ion k in intracellular space, apical and basolateral spaces adjacent to the membrane, respectively, N_f is the number of fixed charges in the cell and w is the volume.

To ensure that the cell volume remains stable over a wide range, we introduce a factor (R_p)

$$R_p = \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{w - 700 \times 10^{-15}}{100 \times 10^{-15}}\right)} \quad [7]$$

This factor reduces the activity of the Na-K pump when the volume exceeds 700 fL. The ATP-dependent Na-K activity is then expressed as $v_{nak} = v_{nak} \times R_p$.

RESULTS

Stability Analysis

Shown in Figure 1 are the contours on the predicted transepithelial potassium current (i_K^{te}) in pA/cell as a function of the K^+ concentration on the apical (endolymph) and basolateral sides of the marginal cell at two different I_{sK} conductances (normal, x5) for control values of ATP (10 mM).

Fig. 1. a) The transepithelial potassium current contours w.r.t. the apical and basal concentrations with normal KCNE1 subunits in the I_{sK} channel. b) The transepithelial potassium current contours w.r.t. apical and basal concentrations with mutated KCNE1 subunits in the I_{sK} channel, which means the K^+ ion permeability for this computation was 5 times the usual. We observe the emergence of a region of hypersensitivity at higher apical and basal K^+ ion concentrations. The dotted lines show the physiological K^+ concentrations in the endolymph and basolateral sides of the marginal cell.

As shown, making the apical potassium channel (KCNE1) overactive has little effect on the system's transepithelial current profile under normal conditions; around the estimated concentration of ~ 4 mM basolateral K^+ . However, a

hypersensitive region arises in higher basolateral concentrations (>15 mM). Due to the small volume of the intrastrial fluid, such concentrations are easily obtainable as a result of ion transport disorders.

To analyze the stability of the steady states achieved above, a linear stability analysis for non-linear systems was used. To do this stability analysis, we computed the Jacobian and eigenvalues of those Jacobians at every steady-state solution corresponding to each combination of apical and basal concentration in the contour plot above. After observing the signs of all the eigenvalues at all these steady-state solutions, we observed that all of those were negative and, hence, stable steady-state solutions.

However, the stability of the solutions does not indicate a biophysically feasible solution. For example, changes in apical and basal concentrations or currents across the marginal cell could change the cell volume or other parameters that might cause cell bursting or death, despite being a steady-state solution of the system of equations.

Marginal Cell Volume Changes as a Result of I_{sk} Mutations and NKCC Blockage

We next examined the predicted changes in marginal cell volume over the range of apical and basal potassium concentrations we studied. As seen in Figure 2, we plot the volume contours on a logarithmic scale, with 0 representing the control volume and 1 representing a 100% percent increase. We predict uncharacteristic increases in the cell volume in these hypersensitive regions, as shown in Figure 2. Cells normally can withstand 40% increases in cell volumes without bursting, as indicated by the purple lines in Fig 2.

Fig 2. This figure shows the normalized cell volume contours in the log10 scale for the various apical and basal K^+ ion concentrations. Note the two purple lines that mark the area around line 0. The 0 line indicates the initial cell volume the computation started with, and the two purple lines denote a +/- 40% in cell volume which is considered a normal range for cell volume to vary without cell bursting or collapsing.

Since it has been established experimentally [5] that blockage of the NKCC cotransporter also causes marginal cell swelling, we were curious to see what the transepithelial K^+ current profiles look like under reduced NKCC activity. In this case, the normal NKCC density has approximately the same transepithelial current profile as that for the normal I_{sK} conductance. However, we also observed hypersensitive regions arising when NKCC density is reduced, as seen in Figure 3, and the states were again stable under the stability analysis.

Fig. 3: a) The transepithelial current contours remain typical, like Fig. 1a) when the NKCC density is unchanged (3.a) and 1.a) are the same plots with different ranges to explicitly show the hypersensitive arising). B) Hypersensitive regions showed up in the transepithelial current contour at about ~ 15 mM basolateral K^+ , when the number of functional NKCC transporters was reduced by half. The dotted lines show the physiological K^+ concentrations in the endolymph and basolateral sides of the marginal cell.

Next, we looked at what combinations of apical and basal concentrations would have the initial volume as the steady-state volume (Figure 4). We computed line 0, which indicates the steady-state volumes that are the same as the initial volume for different NKCC cotransporter densities. From Figure 2, we understand that our physically feasible volume range lies around line 0, and here we observe our line 0 moving to higher apical concentrations when basal concentrations increase for lower NKCC densities. This shows us that lower NKCC densities tend to have more range in volume and can withstand larger marginal cell volumes at higher apical and basal concentrations. The hypersensitive current profile appears at even higher apical and basal concentration combinations. This shows us that hypersensitive transepithelial currents wouldn't arise in a physically feasible volume range similar to the higher I_{sK} conductance case where.

Fig. 4. The initial volume remains the steady-state volume for higher apical K^+ ion concentrations as the activity of the NKCC channel is reduced further.

CONCLUSIONS

The previously observed hypersensitivity in potassium transport across the marginal cell layer that occurs with increased I_{sk} [2] does not result from the emergence of unstable states. Rather, it appears to correlate with increases in cell volume. We also found that the blockage of NKCC by furosemide also resulted in the appearance of hypersensitivity, but this did not correlate with large increases in cell volume, at least up to 50% blockage.

As shown in Figure 2, there is only a narrow bandwidth of apical and basal concentration combinations (in endolymph and intrastrial space) that would result in a biophysically feasible steady-state cell volume. The existing model accounts for cell-volume regulation in terms of R_p that reduces Na-K pump activity. This is an approximate way of treating volume regulation, and more biophysical information is needed on the volume regulation mechanism present in marginal cells. Nevertheless, the model suggests that mutations in ion transport proteins may put osmotic stress on the marginal cells, which could feedback on the mechanics of the cochlea.

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